

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue I, January 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

CLINICAL SUPERVISION PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL HEADS IN GUIMBA DISTRICT

HERSHEY M. LACAMBRA, LPT

Master of Arts in Education
Major in Educational Management Student
Tarlac State University
Tarlac City

ABSTRACT

Title: **CLINICAL SUPERVISION PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL HEADS IN GUIMBA DISTRICT**

Researcher: **HERSHEY M. LACAMBRA**

Institution: **Tarlac State University**

Degree: **Master of Arts in Education**

Major: **Educational Management**

Quality education is one of the seventeen interlinked objectives found in the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations. Undeniably, it is also the battle cry of all educational institutions. The graduates are the living proofs whether an educational institution embodied quality in delivering education or not. This will circle back to the way teachers teach and give instructions inside the classroom, whether physical or virtual.

Neophyte teachers tend to need more nurturing for them to be more efficient in teaching. The statement goes also to the seasoned teachers who refuse innovation. Albeit proficient and experienced teachers still have something to work on to get better for educational trends never cease to emerge and problems are also evolving. Clinical supervision is the term used to the process of giving technical assistance to the teachers inside the classroom coming from their respective school heads which may include master teachers.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

This study aims to present the real state of clinical supervision by means of examining the implementation of the practices under clinical supervision's phases which are pre-conference, observation, and post-observation. It also includes the problems encountered by the school heads in Guimba District with the objective of crafting an action plan.

The researcher used quantitative descriptive research design. A researcher-made survey questionnaire was utilized. It covers the areas on how the school heads conducts clinical supervision and what are the identified challenges.

The study revealed that school heads and master teachers who are both clinical supervisors conduct all the processes under pre-conference, observation, and post-observation religiously.

Problems that surfaced include voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity, time-constraint supervisory feedback after class observation, and lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback.

The action plan proposed by the researcher based on the results of the will help in a better understanding and implementation of clinical supervision.

It is envisioned that this study will be a wake-up call to improve or revise the way clinical supervision is being administered in order to contribute in attaining quality education to produce competent graduates that will help in nation building.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT **Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

CHAPTER 1 **THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND**

Background of the Study

In our modern - day society, the practice of clinical supervision has been accordingly challenged to become increasingly globalized as well. Affirming evidence to that effect can now be seen on a number of fronts, including the organization of important international supervision conferences, and the conduct of cross-continent supervision research (Son & Ellis, 2013).

Clinical supervision is a process for developing responsible teachers who were able to evaluate their own instruction, who were willing to accept criticism and use it for change, and who knew where they were headed in their own professional growth (Sullivan, 2013). Formative evaluation was being imposed in clinical supervision because it increases the efficiency of educational programs being implemented.

Clinical supervision is described as “the formal provisions, by approved supervisors, of a relationship-based education and training that is work-focused and which manages, supports, develops, and evaluates the work of colleagues (Milne & Watkins, 2014). Clinical supervision is currently considered a distinct competency that require specific knowledge, skills and professional practice (Falender & Shafranske, 2017; Gazzola, 2013). All these competencies point out the supervision training of school heads and master teachers who conduct the clinical supervision. The majority of school heads and master teachers conduct supervision based on their own experiences. This practice may result in ineffective interactions and potentially harmful supervisory outcomes (Gazzola, 2013). Also, deliberate or unintentional supervision behavior may lead to ineffective or harmful supervision (Kocyigit, 2019).

The effect of clinical supervision made by the school heads and master teachers is undeniably important to teacher's role in the students' learning process. So, effective supervision is essential for assessing and evaluating supervisees' competencies and professional identity (Gazzola, 2013; Kemer & Borders, 2017) as well as fostering professional development and yielding a gatekeeping role for client welfare (Bernard & Goodyear, 2014).

There are numerous factors in supervision that can cause difficulty for the supervisor and reduce the effectiveness of the supervision. These factors include meeting the needs of the supervisee, agreeing with the supervisee about supervision goals, providing effective feedback, determining the appropriate supervision methods and techniques, and establishing an effective supervision relationship to address multicultural issues ethically (Kocyigit, 2019). Each of these factors can be challenging for the part of the school heads and master teachers in clinical supervision. School heads and master teachers must adapt their style to each teachers' individual needs and personal characteristics. This will provide the most beneficial and effective learning experience as possible (Rhinehart, 2015).

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

At present, our education has shifted its attention from emphasis of quantity to emphasis of quality to improve the condition of our education. This current movement demands that the process of clinical supervision undergo a movement of reform and renewal. In this movement, it seems essential to assess the practices of clinical supervision. Some of our education programs were school improvement program and continuous professional development of teachers. One of which is the DepEd Memo No. 8, series of 2023 known as the Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers which shows four phases of the cycle. Phase two is all about performance monitoring and coaching in which clinical supervision is also done. In the Division of Nueva Ecija, classroom observation is performed by the school head. In the absence of school head or if the elementary or secondary school has a large number of faculty members, master teachers are then instructed to perform this administrative task in compliance to the abovementioned memorandum.

According to Natalia (2020), teachers need to be fostered continuously to achieve the required competencies, because teachers have a role to grow and foster students' abilities professionally when carrying out the teaching and learning process. A professional teacher is someone who has interests and abilities, as well as special specialization related to the teaching field so that he can carry out his duties and obligations as a teacher with the optimal ability (Fauzi, 2020). Related to this, school leaders have a great obligations and task to always accompany and foster teachers to achieve the realization of national education goals. Overcoming this, principals can do so through the supervision of teachers to foster and develop the abilities possessed by teachers on an ongoing basis.

The purpose of supervision is to guide all school staff so that the school staff and teachers can develop their performance, thus fostering a good teaching process atmosphere (Afrijawidiya, 2017). According to Babuta (2019), service is a form of supervision that is more emphasized in its implementation. Supervision has the main object in its implementation, which is related to teaching and learning and efforts to constantly improve deficiencies.

The way teachers gain professional support from school heads and master teachers and the way teachers view the supervision that they are undergoing which is very important in the outcomes of the supervision process. Evaluating, assessing, and improving the practices and working with challenges of clinical supervision is very important in implementing successful supervision (Ekyaw, 2014).

In addition to this, the researcher looks in detail of the challenges faced by school heads and master teachers as well as teachers in the conduct of clinical supervision. So relentless efforts were being made to alleviate the problems for the success of clinical supervision. The current initiation for quality of education further rationalized the researcher to deal in the area under discussion, as supervision was a

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

quality monitoring tool. Indeed, these circumstances initiated the researcher to conduct the study.

Due to this reason, the researcher intended to assess the clinical supervision practices and challenges of Secondary School heads in Guimba District. In doing so, the researcher has raised the following research questions below.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to assess the practices to which clinical supervision was implemented and identify the challenges encountered in the implementation of clinical supervision faced by the secondary school heads in Guimba District.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What clinical supervision practices of the school heads in Guimba District along the following:
 - 1.1. Pre-Conference;
 - 1.2. Observation Phase; and
 - 1.3. Post Conference?
2. What are the clinical supervision challenges encountered by the school heads in Guimba district?
3. What plan of action could be proposed to address the challenges encountered by the school heads?
4. What are the implications of the study to educational management?

Significance of the Study

The study may possibly help the implementation of clinical supervision of school heads in Guimba district since the study will determine the practices applied and challenges encountered in this area.

To the **policy makers**. The study may provide important information that will be a great help to revise and develop appropriate programs.

To the **school heads**. The study may help the school heads to formulate and develop remedial measures against the challenges that secondary schools faced in implementing clinical supervision services.

To the **master teachers**. The study may help master teachers to identify the strength and weaknesses of the practices used in clinical supervision and develop plans on how to improve these practices in order to achieved desired result.

To the **teachers**. The study may help the teachers to be aware of the extent to which clinical supervision is being implemented.

To the **students**. The study will help the students understand the importance of clinical supervision which help their teacher to improve their quality of teaching which affect the teaching and learning process inside the room.

To the **future researchers**. The study may serve as a starting point for other researchers who are interested to do their research on the title.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Scope and Delimitations

The study is delimited only for 11 school heads, 29 master teachers and 480 teachers from the 11 secondary schools in Guimba District as the research participants. The study will be conducted on the First Quarter of school year 2023-2024. The main purpose of the study is to assess the clinical supervision practices and identify the challenges encountered in the implementation of clinical supervision.

Literature Review and Related Studies

One key concern for success of educational institution is to ensure that teachers are well supervised (Stark, McGhee, & Jimerson, 2017). As Adu, Akinloye and Olaoye (2014) narrated, supervision whether internal or external should be considered a deliberate effort aimed at enhancing the outcomes of each educational institution. It is a process of involving teachers in instructional dialogue for the purpose of improving teaching and increasing student achievement (Sullivan & Glanz, 2013).

Supervision is an intervention provided by a superior officer to a subordinate to see that the latter does the expectation appropriately" (Canas, 2017; Bernard & Goodyear, 2014; McNamara, 2013). According to them the advancement of knowledge and skills are not the only focus of educational supervision but also the maturation of the supervisee's behavior.

Supervision is an educational process which should be formed by knowledge and research from relevant fields such as learning theory, teacher education, and cognitive science (Borders, 2010; Goodyear, 2013; Watkins, 2012). Thus, school heads and master teachers who are labelled as clinicians should undergo trainings about the principles and practices that will prepare them and will help them compliment this identity.

Supervision is assessed as a social process that encourages and assist teachers in their professional development, focuses on the learning and teaching activities and evaluates the instruction for improvement (Agaoglu & Ceylan, 2010; Memduhoglu & Zengin, 2012). Supervision aims not only to appraise teachers for improvement of its instructions but also to help teachers to become fully develop professionally.

Supervision process in secondary school chiefly renders direct or immediate assistance towards the improvement of teacher's performance in order to increase student's learning. To achieve this goal of clinical supervision in secondary schools, efforts must be geared toward overcoming most of the challenges facing supervision (lamidi & Afariogu, 2020; Soltani, 2014; Sooksomchitra, 2020).

Clinical supervision is one of the most popular and comprehensive approaches of contemporary supervision (Kemal, 2017). According to Pajak (2010), in the second half of the 21st century, under the circumstances of forcing educational changes, clinical supervision was arisen as an adaptation of the types of supervision approaches

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

helping to preserve the most remarkable classical values of traditional supervision such as rationality, decentralization and problem solving – based on cooperation.

Clinical supervision includes practices that revamp the behavior of the teacher inside the classroom that improves student's learning. This supervision follows observation, analysis, strategic planning, conference and post conference analyze (Gold, 2014).

The essential goals of clinical supervision are to protect client welfare and support the professional development of the person being supervised. (Aasheim, 2012). In order to accomplish these goals, school head and master teacher must forge a harmonious professional relationship and offer counsel or direction whenever needed.

Undoubtedly, the most significant supervision and guidance in the school setting was given by the school heads of the school (Mofarch, 2011). A school's objectives can be achieved through effective and timely supervision. These school heads and master teachers execute supervision through numerous practices including direct supervision to teachers.

One of the various functions of the school principal is to provide guidance and direction to the teacher's fulfillment of tasks. It means that principals are accountable for helping teachers do their job better by joint efforts (Kotirde and Yunos, 2015). They are key elements in a sound and sensible management of people, tools, and equipment for a smooth and promising school operation According to Kotirde and Yunos (2015), principals execute the following functions in the exercise of their supervisory mandate: a) mentoring inexperienced teachers to promote a supportive entry into the profession; b) raising teachers to minimum standards of successful teaching through daily coaching and in-service training; c) continuous development of case skills for individual teachers; d) working together with different groups of teachers to enhance the learning of students; e) working with teachers to adapt and coordinate the school curriculum to meet the needs of students and to be on the path to approved education standards.

In some cases, principals do not involve teachers in formulating school rules and providing new teachers with mentorship to facilitate supportive induction (Onyali & Akinfolarin, 2017). More so, the attitude of fault – finding among supervisors, lack of motivation for teachers, lack of training and retraining of teachers through refresher courses, nomenclature of teachers and irregular allocation of funds to provide in – service capacity building training are some of the issues facing adequate supervision (Tubosun & Umar, 2016; Dewodo et al., 2020).

The supervisory process has recently changed from looking for deficiency to improvement (Glickman, Gordon & Ross – Gordon, 2013). In the same sense, the basic function of the contemporary supervision approach stressing improvement is to evaluate students' successes and teachers' performances, to monitor curriculum and instruction, and to develop them (Pajak, 2010).

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT **Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024)/ International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

To improve teachers' instructional performance, school heads and master teachers as clinicians should work collaboratively with their teachers. Thus, in order to bring effective education through the improved teaching – learning process; instructional supervisors should be democratic and cooperative and should get serious attention in the school (Adu, 2014). The collaborative effort between teachers, master teachers and school heads are very important in the supervisory process. This would help in reforming the way this practice was instituted and may possibly abstain from probable conflicts in the future.

Osakwe (2010) discovered a important relationship between the supervisory strategies of the school head and instructional abilities of the teachers in terms of tangible instructional aids and imposing and maintaining discipline. In the study carefully conducted by Alimi and Akinfolarin (2012), it has been revealed that activities such as looking at the student's notes, class drills, classroom visitations, scrutinizing test questions before test paper reproduction, and tracking student's progress in their academic standing is vital. Thus, the assessment of students in any educational setting is of paramount importance to the success of such institutions (Ampofo, Bizimana, Mbuti, Ndayambaje & Orondtho, 2014). Teachers are expected to religiously assess students with the purpose of improving student's performance, whereas school heads supervise the proper practice of teacher's assigned roles and functions including assessments of students.

In the Indian context, Tyagi (2010) emphasized that direct supervision creates a platform for both teachers and school heads to use their collective expertise in self – appraisal of teachers, to identify gaps in teacher skills, knowledge and competencies in order to provide the vital support needed for teachers' professional development.

Research studies in Africa claimed that enhancement and advancement of educational sectors is related to the efficient instructional supervision practices of the heads through direct supervision. In the findings of a study by Wanzare (2011) on instructional supervision in public secondary schools showed that school heads' direct supervision improves the quality of teachers and teaching, facilitates students' academic performance and provides the opportunity to monitor teachers' instructional work. Panigrahi's (2012) study on implementation of instructional supervision in secondary schools in Ethiopia found that classroom visits enable head teachers to interact with teachers, determine whether teachers are issuing sound instruction and provide feedback to help teachers correct highlighted issues.

In the study on transforming teachers' instructional practices through clinical supervision, Williams, Baksh and James (2019) observed that there are challenges to clinical supervision: defensive reactions by teachers; adaptation to suit individual needs; supervisors' knowledge of techniques to be used during clinical supervision and finding the time for supervision. In general, clinical supervision process provides assistance in enhancing the teachers' way of providing instructions inside the

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

classroom. On the other hand, teachers may behave defensively when faced with supervision, unless teachers perceived supervision as an aid and a way of increasing their level of proficiency that will reflect positively their students' academic performance.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the study

The paradigm shows that in implementing clinical supervision at the school level, different practices were used by the school heads and master teachers. Challenges were faced and identified, and the possible proposed action plan were formulated. The result of the study will have an implication to educational management

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT **Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

CHAPTER 2 **METHODS OF STUDY AND SOURCES OF DATA**

Research Design

The study used a quantitative descriptive research design that uses a survey questionnaire to acquire comprehensive understanding of clinical supervision practices and challenges of secondary school heads, master teacher, and teachers. According to Mertler (2014), the purpose of descriptive research is to describe and interpret the current status of individuals, settings, conditions or events. The numerical data collected can be counted, tallied, or rated and is usually collected through surveys or questionnaires (Mertler, 2014).

Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted in Guimba District in Nueva Ecija. The researcher also gathered respondents through random sampling from each secondary schools in Guimba District, Nueva Ecija. The researcher hand picked the place of implementation because it will provide the researcher the necessary data to evaluate the clinical supervision practices and challenges of school heads, master teachers and teachers in secondary in Guimba District. The study was conducted on the First Quarter of the School Year 2023 – 2024.

Sampling Design

There is one type of sampling technique that was used in this study. This is simple random sampling. The technique was employed to ensure that every member of the population has an equal chance of being selected and it is favorable to homogenous and uniformly selected population (Noor, Tajik, Golzar, 2022). This was achieved by writing out the names of the school heads on a piece of paper which was folded and put in a drop box. After thorough reshuffling, the researcher draws lots a school head then records it in a summary paper that will serve as the master list of selected respondents. The same process was also applied in obtaining the quantity of samples from the master teachers and teacher respondents.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Participants

The participants in this study were the 11 school heads, 16 master teachers and 408 teachers who are currently serving as school heads, master teachers, and teachers in secondary schools in Guimba District for the school year 2023 - 2024.

Sample Schools	School Heads	Master Teachers	Teachers	Respondents
GUIMBA WEST				
Pacac High School	1	0	21	22
Galvan High School	1	4	50	55
Macatcatuit High School	1	0	17	18
Maybubon Integrated School	1	0	24	25
GUIMBA EAST				
Bartolome Sangalang NHS	1	4	150	155
San Andres High School	1	0	21	22
Manacsac High School	1	1	21	23
Nagpandayan High School	1	0	25	26
Triala National High School	1	5	37	43
San Bernardino Integrated School	1	1	23	25
Bunol Integrated School	1	1	19	21
Total:	11	16	408	435

Table 1: Summary of Schools, School Heads, Master Teachers and Teacher Respondents

Eleven (11) school heads, eleven (11) master teachers and two hundred two (202) teachers were randomly selected using the Slovin's formula with 95% level of significance at 0.05 margin of error. A total of two hundred twenty – four (224) were the respondents of the study.

Respondents	Population	Sample
School Heads	11	11
Master Teachers	16	11
Teachers	408	202

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Total Respondents:	435	224
--------------------	-----	-----

Table 2: Summary of Population and Sample School Heads, Sample Master Teachers and Sample Teacher Respondents

Research Instruments

The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire which is composed of four parts. The first part is used to gather the needed data about the general information of the respondents. The second part are the practices and procedures in clinical supervision during the pre-conference, observation phase and post conference. The third part are the challenges encountered in clinical supervision. The fourth part is composed of an open-ended question about clinical supervisions. Opinions of experts such as two school heads and one district supervisor were taken into consideration in order to test the validity of the instrument. The improved version underwent pilot study and the alpha reliability of the test was computed using Cronbach's Alpha Test.

Data Gathering Procedure

The first step in this study was securing a letter to conduct the study from the Division Office of Guimba District then an endorsement letter was released and sent to the District Office then later on to the office of the principal. It was followed by the construction of the researcher – made survey questionnaire that will be used to gather information about the respondents' general information, clinical supervision practices and challenges encountered. The researcher – made survey questionnaire was validated by the school heads and district supervisor in Guimba District and underwent pilot study and reliability test.

A total of two hundred twenty-four (224) respondents were randomly selected which is composed of eleven (11) school heads, eleven (11) master teachers, and two hundred two (202) teachers to become the respondents of the study.

Statistical Treatment / Data Analysis

To interpret the data, statistical analysis is used in quantitative research. The data gathered from the field is numerical and can be formulated using statistical method. The data will be subjected to statistical treatment in order to answer the questions proposed in the study.

The researcher decided to incorporate the 5 – point Likert Scale in the research instrument as it provides a great way of measuring the clinical supervision practices and challenges encountered by the school heads in Guimba District that the researcher evaluated.

Scale	Interval	Equivalent Response
5	4.20 – 5.00	Always
4	3.40 – 4.19	Offentimes

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

3	2.60 – 3.39	Sometimes
2	1.80 – 2.59	Seldom
2	1.00 – 1.79	Never

To determine the clinical supervision practice of the school heads in Guimba District along the pre-conference, observation phase, and post conference, weighted mean was used.

To determine the challenges encountered in clinical supervision faced by the school heads in Guimba District, frequency, percentage and rank distribution was used.

Ethical Consideration

In any research study that involves human as subjects, harms and potential errors will be avoided if ethics is considered. To ensure that the research study followed high ethical standards, data procurement and interpretation processes were thoroughly followed.

Participants of the study are well-informed through a quick orientation of the objectives of the research and its procedure. The researcher also explained in a descriptive manner the ways of collecting the data. After which, if the participant agreed to proceed with the process of being interviewed and surveyed, they received a letter of consent prior to the interview and survey reassuring that anonymity and confidentiality will be practiced and details will be taken care of properly. This is to assure that their participation to the study will not inflict and physically, moreover professional, harm to them at all. Anonymity was maintained even during the analyzation of data from the interview and survey by using the letters of the alphabet from A-Z to name all the subjects.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

CHAPTER 3
PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to answer the sub-problem relative to the main problem of this study clinical supervision practices and challenges of secondary school heads in Guimba District. This chapter discusses the findings of the study based on the research questions.

1. Clinical Supervision Practices of the School Heads in Guimba District

The clinical supervision practices of the supervisors, namely the school head and/or master teachers, play a pivotal role to improve the supervisee's ability to improve classroom setting.

1.1 Pre-Conference Phase

The clinical supervisors are encouraged to discuss the data collection strategies as regards to the teachers' and students' behavior with a focus on the area to be observed. Tables 3 and 4 present the clinical supervision practices of the school heads in Guimba District during the Pre – Conference Phase as revealed by the Teacher, Master Teacher and School Head.

Table 3: Clinical Supervision Practices of the School Heads in Guimba District during the Pre – Conference Phase as Revealed by the Teacher

PRE – CONFERENCE	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The school head ...			
1. conducts the pre-observation conference.	4.54	9.28	Always
2. communicates to you the main purpose / focus of the class visit / observation clearly.	4.47	10.50	Always
3. checks your lesson plan before the class observation.	4.48	12.27	Always
4. makes a discussion on the methodology of the lesson before the presentation.	4.50	9.41	Always
5. plans with you about the specifics of the observation during this phase to have a conceptual framework for the observation.	4.49	9.41	Always

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

It can be seen in the table above that during the Pre – Conference Phase as revealed by the teacher, the school head conducts the pre – observation conference obtained a mean of 4.54 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head communicates to you the main purpose / focus of the class visit / observation clearly obtained a mean of 4.47 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head checks your lesson plan before the class observation obtained a mean of 4.48 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head makes a discussion on the methodology of the lesson before the presentation obtained a mean of 4.50 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head plans with you about the specifics of the observation during this phase to have a conceptual framework for the observation obtained a mean of 4.49 with verbal interpretation of always. This means that the majority of the school heads always conduct the pre – observation conference.

Table 4
Clinical Supervision Practices of the School Heads in Guimba District during the Pre – Conference Phase as Revealed by the Master Teacher and School Head

PRE – CONFERENCE	Master Teacher		School Head		Grand Mean	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
As a Head Teacher / Master Teacher, I...						
1. conduct the pre-observation conference	4.92	0.96	4.90	0.95	4.91	Always
2. communicate the teacher the main purpose / focus of the class visit / observation clearly.	4.92	0.96	4.80	1.26	4.86	Always
3. check the lesson plan of the teacher before the class observation.	4.83	1.29	4.70	1.45	4.77	Always
4. ask the methodology/ies to be used in presenting the lesson.	4.75	1.5	4.60	1.55	4.68	Always
5. plan with the teacher about the specifics of the	4.92	0.96	4.60	1.55	4.76	Always

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

observation during this phase to have a conceptual framework for the observation.						
---	--	--	--	--	--	--

It can be seen in the table above that during the Pre – Conference Phase as revealed by the master teacher and school head, the school head conducts the pre – observation conference obtained a mean of 4.91 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head communicates to the teacher the main purpose / focus of the class visit / observation clearly obtained a mean of 4.86 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head check the lesson plan of the teacher before the class observation obtained a mean of 4.77 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head asks the methodology/ies to be used in presenting the lesson obtained a mean of 4.68 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head plan with the teacher about the specifics of the observation during this phase to have a conceptual framework for the observation obtained a mean of 4. with verbal interpretation of always. This means that the majority of the school heads always conduct the pre-observation conference.

Table 5 presents the clinical supervision practices of the school heads in Guimba District during the Observation Phase as revealed by the Teacher.

1.2 Observation Phase

Classroom interactions is the focus of this part. The supervisors attend the class and gathers the data as agreed on during the pre – observation meeting. The data collection can take the form of notes, tapes, and videos. The succeeding tables show the practices of the respondents of the study.

Table 5: Clinical Supervision Practices of the School Heads in Guimba District during the Observation Phase as Revealed by the Teacher

OBSERVATION PHASE	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The school head ...			
1. conducts the class observation based on the framework articulated in Pre-Conference phase.	4.59	9.22	Always
2. attends the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end.	4.70	8.64	Always

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

3. makes frequent class visit to provide support for the teacher.	4.39	11.48	Always
4. records data of the teacher's performance and the students' activities.	4.63	9.32	Always
5. focuses only on the teachers' teaching behaviors and instructional methodology.	4.42	11.18	Always

The table revealed that during the observation phase as revealed by the teacher, the school head conducts the class observation based on the framework articulated in Pre-Conference Phase obtained a mean of 4.59 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head attends the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end obtained a mean of 4.70 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head makes frequent class visit to provide support for the teacher obtained a mean of 4.39 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head records data of the teacher's performance and the student's activities obtained a mean of 4.63 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head focuses only on the teachers' teaching behaviors and instructional methodology obtained a mean of 4.42 with standard deviation of 11.18 with verbal interpretation of. This means that majority of the school heads always attends the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end.

Table 6: Clinical Supervision Practices of the School Heads in Guimba District during the Observation Phase as Revealed by the Master Teacher and School Head

OBSERVATION PHASE	Master Teacher		School Head		Grand Mean	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
As a Head Teacher / Master Teacher, I...						
1. conduct the class observation based on the framework articulated in Pre-Conference Phase	4.92	0.96	4.60	1.55	4.76	Always
2. attend the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end.	4.83	1.29	4.90	0.95	4.87	Always

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

3. make frequent class visit to provide support for the teacher.	4.33	1.63	4.40	1.55	4.37	Always
4. record data of the teacher's performance and the students' activities.	4.67	1.63	4.60	1.55	4.63	Always
5. focus only on teachers' teaching behaviors and instructional methodology.	4.42	2.99	4.50	2.12	4.46	Always

The table showed that during the observation phase as revealed by the master teacher and the school head, the school head conducts the class observation based on the framework articulated in Pre-Conference Phase obtained a mean of 4.76 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head attends the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end obtained a mean of 4.87 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head makes frequent class visit to provide support for the teacher obtained a mean of 4.37 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head records data of the teacher's performance and the student's activities obtained a mean of 4.63 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head focuses only on the teachers' teaching behaviors and instructional methodology obtained a mean of 4.46 with verbal interpretation of always. This means that majority of the school heads always attend the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end.

1.3 Observation Phase

The post conference phase is of paramount importance as it provides the teacher with objective feedback on the current state of his / her instruction by diagnosing and solve instructional problems. The following tables present the data collected concerning post-conference phase.

Table 7: Clinical Supervision Practices of the School Heads in Guimba District during the Post Conference Phase as Revealed by the Teacher

POST CONFERENCE	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The School Head...			
1. gives immediate feedback (face to face) to the teachers after the classroom observation.	4.81	6.59	Always

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

2. involves the teacher in the process of analyzing and interpreting the collected data.	4.68	8.37	Always
3. discusses with the teacher better strategies for the next session of clinical supervision.	4.71	8.47	Always
4. provides well-organized feedback on the objectives, methods, contents, student's activities, and assessments observed during the class observation.	4.64	8.16	Always
5. makes an arrangement for the next class observation if necessary.	4.61	8.48	Always

It can be seen in the table that during the post conference phase as revealed by the teacher, the school head gives immediate feedback (face to face) to the teacher after the classroom observation obtained a mean of 4.81 with verbal interpretation of very high. The school head involves the teacher in the process of analyzing and interpreting the collected data obtained a mean of 4.68 with verbal interpretation of very high. The school head discusses with the teacher better strategies for the next session of clinical supervision obtained a mean of 4.71 with verbal interpretation of very high. The school head provides well-organized feedback on the objectives, methods, contents, student's activities, and assessments observed during the class observation obtained a mean of 4.64 with verbal interpretation of very high. The school head makes an arrangement for the next class observation, if necessary, obtained a mean of 4.61 with verbal interpretation of very high. This means that majority of the school head gives immediate feedback (face to face) to the teacher after the classroom observation.

Table 8: Clinical Supervision Practices of the School Heads in Guimba District during the Post Conference Phase as Revealed by the Master Teacher and School Head

POST CONFERENCE	Master Teacher		School Head		Grand Mean	Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
As a Head Teacher / Master Teacher, I...						
1. give immediate feedback (face to face) to the teachers after the classroom observation.	4.92	0.96	4.90	0.95	4.91	Always

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

2. involve the teacher in the process of analyzing and interpreting the collected data.	4.92	0.96	4.80	1.27	4.86	Always
3. discuss with the teacher better strategies for the next session of clinical supervision.	4.83	1.29	4.80	1.27	4.81	Always
4. provides well-organized feedback on the objectives, methods, contents, student's activities, and assessments observed during the class observation.	4.92	0.96	4.70	1.58	4.81	Always
5. make an arrangement for the next class observation if necessary.	4.83	1.29	4.70	1.45	4.77	Always

The table revealed that during the post conference phase as revealed by the master teacher and school head, the school head give immediate feedback (face to face) to the teacher after the classroom observation obtained a mean of 4.91 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head involves the teacher in the process of analyzing and interpreting the collected data obtained a mean of 4.86 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head discusses with the teacher better strategies for the next session of clinical supervision obtained a mean of 4.81 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head provides well-organized feedback on the objectives, methods, contents, student's activities, and assessments observed during the class observation obtained a mean of 4.81 with verbal interpretation of always. The school head makes an arrangement for the next class observation, if necessary, obtained a mean of 4.77 with verbal interpretation of always. This means that majority of the school head gives immediate feedback (face to face) to the teacher after the classroom observation.

2. Clinical Supervision Challenges Encountered by the School Heads in Guimba District

In any educational processes, flawlessness of the ways is sought to be achieved. However, problems are inevitable. Clinical supervision as a process has its

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

own flaws. The Tables below show the clinical supervision challenges encountered by the school head in Guimba District.

Table 9: Clinical Supervision Challenges Encountered by the School Head in Guimba District as Revealed by the Teacher

Indicator	f	%	Rank
Voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity	47	17.74	1
Great number of teachers in the school	44	16.60	2
Time constraint supervisory feedback after class Observation	35	13.21	3
Lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback	28	10.57	4
Insufficient regular class visitation	26	9.81	5
Teacher's negative attitude towards the clinical supervision activity	22	8.30	6
School head's qualifications to implement the clinical supervision tasks and providing professional support to teachers	19	7.17	7
Insufficient supervisory trainings	17	6.42	8
School head's insufficient knowledge and skills of giving professional support to the teachers for the improvement of the teaching-learning process	15	5.66	9
Inadequate communication skills of the school head to motivate, inspire and guide the teacher	12	4.52	10

Based on the data in the table above, the top 5 clinical supervision challenges encountered by the school heads were 1.) voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity, 2.) great number of teachers in the school, 3.) time constraint supervisory feedback after class observation, 4.) lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback, and 5.) insufficient regular class visitation.

The findings imply that there are problems encountered in the practice of clinical supervision that need to be addressed notably in terms of performing administrative tasks other than supervisory activity considering there are large number of teachers that needs to be supervise.

Table 10: Clinical Supervision Challenges Encountered by the School Head

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

in Guimba District as Revealed by the Master Teacher and School Head

Indicator	F	%	Rank
Voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity	6	21.43	1
Time constraint supervisory feedback after class observation	5	17.86	2.5
Lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback	5	17.86	2.5
Teacher's negative attitude towards the clinical supervision activity	3	10.71	4.5
Insufficient supervisory trainings	3	10.71	4.5
School head's insufficient knowledge and skills of giving professional support to the teachers for the improvement of the teaching-learning process	1	3.57	6.5
School head's qualifications to implement the clinical supervision tasks and providing professional support to teachers	1	3.57	6.5
Great number of teachers in the school	2	7.14	8.5
Insufficient regular class visitation	2	7.14	8.5
Inadequate communication skills of the school head to motivate, inspire and guide the teacher	0		10

Based on the data in the table above, the top 5 clinical supervision challenges encountered by the school heads were 1.) voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity, 2.) time constraint supervisory feedback after class observation, 3.) lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback 4.) teacher's negative attitude towards the clinical supervision activity, and 5.) insufficient supervisory trainings.

The findings imply that there are problems encountered in the practice of clinical supervision in terms voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity as revealed by the school head.

Table 11: Clinical Supervision Challenges Encountered by the School Head in Guimba District as Revealed by Teacher, Master Teacher and School Head

Indicator	Rank as Revealed by Teacher	Rank as Revealed by School Head	Rank
Voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity	1	1	1

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Time constraint supervisory feedback after class observation	3	2.5	2
Lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback	4	2.5	3
Great number of teachers in the school	2	8.5	4.5
Teacher's negative attitude towards the clinical supervision activity	6	4.5	4.5
Insufficient supervisory trainings	8	4.5	6
School head's qualifications to implement the clinical supervision tasks and providing professional support to teachers	7	6.5	7.5
Insufficient regular class visitation	5	8.5	7.5
School head's insufficient knowledge and skills of giving professional support to the teachers for the improvement of the teaching-learning process	9	6.5	9
Inadequate communication skills of the school head to motivate, inspire and guide the teacher	10	10	10

Based on the data in the table above, the top 5 clinical supervision challenges encountered by the school heads as revealed by the teacher and the school head are 1.) voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity, 2.) time constraint supervisory feedback after class observation, 3.) lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback, 4.) great number of teachers, and 5.) teacher's negative attitude towards the clinical supervision activity.

As argued by Lovell and Wiles in their research paper year 1983, usage of only one model with three steps is not applicable to all teachers, given that there are individual differences. With that being said, problems will surely arise while implementing clinical supervision. Gordon (1992) believes that clinical supervision is not accepted by many because of the notion that the supervisor is adept to his identity as clinician. These statement of Gordon is supported by the research of Cogan (1973) that undeveloped trust and respect between the supervisor and supervisee is a problem in making supervision effective.

3. Proposed Plan of Action to Address the Challenges Encountered by the School Heads

Based on the gathered data, the School Head of Guimba Districts experience challenges in implementing clinical supervision. The proposed action plan for the clinical was designed by the researcher focused on the weakness found in the study. The table below shows a year-round action plan. The primary objective of this action plan is to help improved the clinical supervision practice in the school.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Table 12: Proposed Plan of Action to Address the Challenges Encountered by the School Heads

Areas of Concern	Objective	Strategies / Activities	Resources	Time Frame	Budget	Expected Outcome
Voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity	To delegate some of the responsibilities of the school head to other personnel	-Delegate administrative tasks to qualified faculty members, provided that they will be given equivalent teaching load to the administrative task. -Propose and implement more efficient administrative processes. -Prioritize supervisory activities and allocate specific time slots for these tasks each week.	Department Heads, Master Teacher, and School Head	Monthly	School MOOE	Responsibilities and other tasks of the school head were distributed to other personnel
Time-constraint supervisory feedback after class observation.	To develop a streamlined and effective feedback process	-Develop a streamlined feedback process for post-observation supervision based on the	Master Teacher and School Head	Quarterly	School MOOE	Detailed and rich in discussion feedback of the observed class

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

	for post-observation supervision based on the PPST domains	PPST domains. -Implement an effective and efficient feedback mechanism for post-observation supervision based on the PPST domains.				
Lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback.	To conduct thorough monitoring and evaluation of past observation	-Develop monitoring and evaluation tool to track the made activities to check the full implementation. -Establish regular review meetings to assess progress and address any challenges in implementing recommendations.	Master Teacher and School Head	Monthly	School MOOE	Documented observations of teacher's past performance, current implementation of recommendations, and progress tracking.
Great number of teachers in the school	To divide the number of	-Delegate supervisory responsibilities of School	Department Heads, Master	Quarterly	School MOOE	Teachers were divided into groups and all

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

	teachers into cluster or groups to conduct the supervisory activity	Heads to Master Teachers and experienced teachers. -Implement a Teacher-Mentorship program pairing experienced teachers with newer ones to provide support and guidance.	Teacher, and School Head			teachers have participated in the supervisory activity
Teacher's negative attitude towards the clinical supervision activity	To provide teachers adequate knowledge of clinical supervision importance	-Attend clinical supervision trainings, seminars, and workshops. -Conduct peer-evaluation to give first-hand experience of clinical supervision.	Teachers	Annually	School MOOE	Constructive criticism tolerant teachers

4. Implications of the Study to Educational Management

The study has revealed a clear picture of the real state of clinical supervision practices and challenges of school heads in Guimba District.

The researcher has the main objective on looking into the different practices implemented and challenges encountered in clinical supervision and as an proactive school administrator of an educational institution, the researcher is also offering a

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

proposal as means of addressing the challenges encountered in the implementation of clinical supervision.

Clinical supervision nearly takes the lion's share in the improvement of the ways teachers deliver their lesson. Successful clinical supervision will help the teachers to become more effective in their jobs and it can contribute to the development or enhancement of the teacher's personality of being tactical and independent when instructional problems arise. All of these will greatly contribute to a higher academic performance of the learners.

The results proved the importance of conducting clinical supervision where experienced individuals gives coaching to the inexperienced ones. It also shows that there are challenges being encountered in the implementation of clinical supervision. Thus, policy makers should revise or create a new program on how school administrators can practice clinical supervision flawlessly. This study is believed to be of considerable value to educational management since it revealed inconspicuous problems in conducting clinical supervision. This could be a wake-up call for educational authorities to improve the practices, consider the issues and address challenges encountered.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusion, and the corresponding recommendations.

Summary

The study generated the following findings:

1. In terms of clinical supervision practices of school heads as revealed by the teacher, master teacher and school head respondents, the school head conducts the pre-observation conference in the Pre – Conference Phase, the school head attends the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end in the Observation Phase, and the school head gives immediate feedback (face to face) to the teachers after the classroom observation in the Post-Observation Phase.
2. The top 5 challenges encountered by the school head and teacher respondents in Guimba District were a.) voluminous administrative tasks other than supervisory activity, b.) time-constraint supervisory feedback after class observation, c.) lack of monitoring and evaluation on the application of recommendations and corrections from the feedback, d.) great number of teachers in the school, and e.) teacher's negative attitude towards the clinical supervision activity.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. It has been the practice of the school heads to conduct the pre – observation conference during pre – conference phase, attend the class observation from the beginning of the period to the end during the observation phase, and gives immediate feedback (face to face) to the teacher after the classroom visitation during the post conference phase.
2. There are some challenges encountered in the practice of clinical supervision by the school heads in Guimba District.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

1. The findings of the study most especially the challenges disclosed by the school head and teacher respondents should be addressed by the school administrators and the school supervisors.
2. School heads should improve their supervisory competence through training and retooling / reskilling program for them to be able to supervise their teachers.
3. The school head should change their teacher's negative attitude towards clinical supervision by initiating a conversation where teachers feel comfortable and safe in stating their real state regarding instructional management.
4. Completing the evaluation process requires feedback. School heads must see to it the feedback, through constructive criticisms, are given. A documentation of the highlighted instructional problem of the teacher should be kept by the school head in order for him/her to track the progress of the teacher after solution has been discussed and agreed upon during the post-conference phase.
5. The school head should show empirical evidence how clinical supervision helped teachers became better in giving instructions and explain that fear is not necessary for clinical supervision, albeit being part of a normal administrative procedure to measure their ability to teach, is rooted in the aim of helping them to improve and boost their performance.
6. The school head and teachers should think of an income generating project to have enough budget allocation to implement clinical supervision activity.
7. In-Service training programs for clinical supervision and topics related to the development of an identity as a clinician should be enthusiastically participated by both the school head and master teachers. This will ensure that they are not only basing their comments and suggestions from their own

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

- experiences, which may not be applicable to all, but through tested and proven helpful practices and principles.
8. To conduct clinical supervision through and through, without worrying much of the time spent and time left to other administrative tasks, the school head must delegate some of his/her supervisory responsibilities that department heads, head teachers and master teachers can do. This requires empowerment from the school head to be guaranteed that tasks delegated are being carried out correctly.
 9. The school should provide their school head, department heads, master teacher adequate trainings, seminars, and workshop about clinical supervision in order for them to supervise their teachers.
 10. A similar study should be conducted by other researchers to validate the findings of the study.

Limitation of the Study

The study is delimited only for school head and teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Guimba District as the research participants. The study will be conducted on the First Quarter of the school year 2023 – 2024. The main purpose of the study is to assess the clinical supervision practices and challenges encountered by the school heads in Guimba District.

REFERENCE LIST

- Aasheim, L. (2012). *Practical Clinical Supervision for Counselors: An Experiential Guide*. Springer Publishing Co. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2011-24770-000>
- Adu, E. O., Akinloye, G.M., & Olaoye, O.F. (2014). Internal and External School Supervision Issues, Challenges and Way Forward. *International Journal of Education Sciences*, 7, 269-278, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09751122.2014.11890189>
- Afrijawidiya, A., Zakaria, Z., & Juarsa, O. (2017). Supervisi Pengajaran Dengan Pendekatan Direktif, Non-Direktif, Dan Kolaboratif, *Manajer Pendidikan*, 11 (4), 325-335
- Agaoglu, E. & Ceylan, M., Egitim denetçilerinin danismanlik rolu ve danismanlik modelleri. *Ilkogretim Online*, 9(2), 541-551, 2010
- Alimi, O.S. and Akinfolarin, C.A. (2012). Impact of Selected Modes of Instructional Supervision Activities on Students' Academic Performance in Senior Secondary

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessedy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Education Research Journal*. 2(1), 1-6

- Ampofo, S.Y., Bizimana, B., Mbuti, J., Ndayambaje, I., & Orodho, J.A. (2014). Performance Discrepancies between formative and Summative Assessments: Focus on Six Different Higher Learning Institutions from Ghana, Kenya and Rwanda. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 5(7), 1386-1393
- Babuta, A.L. & Rahmat, A. (2019). Peningkatan Kompetensi Pedagogik Guru Melalui Pelaksanaan Supervisi Klinis Dengan Teknik Kelompok, *AL – TANZIM: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 3(1), 1-28 [https:// doi.org/10.33650/al-tanzim.v3il.496](https://doi.org/10.33650/al-tanzim.v3il.496)
- Bencherab, A. & Maskari, A.A. (2021). Clinical Supervision: A Genius Tool for Teachers' Professional Growth, *The Universal Academic Research Journal*, 3(2), 51-57
- Bernard, J.M., & Goodyear, R. (2014). *Fundamentals of Clinical Supervision (5th Edition)* Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education Inc.
- Borders, L.D. (2010). Principles of Best Practices for Clinical supervisor training programs. In J.R. Culbreth L. Brown (Eds), *State of the Art in Clinical Supervision* pp. 127-150. New York: Routledge
- Canas, W.P. (2017). Definition, Nature and Functions of Supervision. Retrieved June 16th, 2019 from www.pressreader.com
- Collins, J., & Hussey, R. (2014). *Business research: a practical guide for undergraduate & postgraduate students (Fourth Edition)*. Place of Publication not identified: Palgrave MacMillan
- Dewodo, C.Y., Dzakpasu, P.E., Agbetorwoka, A. (2020). Perception of Teachers on Instructional Supervision at Basic Schools in Hohoe Municipality of Ghana. *Am. J. Educ. Inform. Technol.* 4(1), 33-40
- Ekyaw, B.A. (2014). *The Practices and challenges of Instructional Supervision in Asossa Zone Primary Schools*. Unpublished Doctoral Thesis), Jimma University, Ethiopia
- Falender, C.A., Shafranske, E.P. (2017). *Supervision Essentials for the Practice of Competency – Based Supervision*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

-
- Fauzi, F. (2020). Peningkatan Profesionalisme Guru Melalui Supervisi Klinis. *EDUSIANA: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Pendidikan Islam*, 7(2), 109-128
- Gazzola, N., De Stefano, J., Theriault, A., & Audet, C.T. (2013) Learning to be Supervisors. A Qualitative Investigation of Difficulties experienced by Supervisors-In-Training. *The Clinical Supervisor*, 32(1), 15-39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07325223.2013.778678>
- Glickman, C.D., Gordon, S.P. & Ross-Gordon, J.M. (2013). *Supervision and Instructional Leadership: A developmental Approach (9th Ed)*. New York: Pearson
- Gold, H.R. (2014). *Clinical Supervision: Special Method for the Supervision of Teachers*. New York: Holt Rinehart Press
- Goodyear, R.K. (2013). Clinical Supervision Effectiveness: What Works, what does not, and to what extent? Presentation at the Ninth International Disciplinary Conference on Clinical Supervision, Adelphi University, New York
- Kalule, I., & Bouchamma, Y. (2014). Teacher Supervision Practices and Characteristics of In-School Supervisors in Uganda, *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, 26, 51-71. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-013-9181-y>
- Kayikci, K., Yilmaz, O., & Sahin, A. (2017). The Views of Educational Supervisors on Clinical Supervision. *Journal of Education and Practice* Vol.8, 159-160. Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University. Alanya, Antalya, Turkey
- Kemer, G., & Borders, D.L. (2017). Expert Clinical Supervisors' Description of Easy and Challenging Supervisees. *The Journal of Counselor Preparation and Supervision*, 9(1), 63-87. <https://doi.org/10.7729/91.1151>
- Kim, H., Sefcik, J.S., Bradway, C. (2017). Characteristics of Qualitative Descriptive Studies: A Systematic Review. *Research in Nursing & Health* 40: 23-42, [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Kocyigit, M. (2019). Challenges and Ethical Issues in Counseling Supervision from Faculty Supervisors' Perspective. *Participatory Educational Research*. Akdeniz University, Antalya Turkey

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

-
- Kotirde, I.Y., Yunos, J.B. (2015). The Processes of Supervisions in Secondary Schools Educational System in Nigeria: 4th World Congress on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (WoCTVET). *J. Soc. Behav. Sci.* 259-264
- Lamidi, M.L., & Afariogun, A.A. (2020). Imperatives of Supervision in Attaining Quality Assurance in Nigerian Educational System. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Educational Planning Administration*, 5(2), 72-84
- McNamara, C. (2013). A Definition of Supervision. Retrieved May 15, 2019 from www.managementhelp.org
- Mertler, C. (2014). *Action Research: Improving schools and empowering educators*. 4th Ed
- Milne, D.L., & Watkins, C.E. (2014). Defining and Understanding Clinical Supervision: A Functional Approach. In: Watkins CE, Milne DL, Editors. *The Wiley International Handbook of Clinical Supervision*, Chichester: Wiley, 2014
- Mofarch, A. (2011). *School – Based Instructional Supervision in Saudi Arabian Public Secondary Schools*, (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis), University of York, York.
- Natalia, N. (2020). Meningkatkan Profesionalisme Guru Dalam Proses Pembelajaran Melalui Supervisi Klinis. *Jurnal Kansasi*, 5(2), 242-250.
<https://doi.org/10.31932/jpbs.v1i1.62>
- Onyali, L.C., Akinfolarin, A.V. (2017). Principal's Application of Instructional Leadership Practices for Secondary School Effectiveness in Oyo State. *J. Niger. Acad. Educ.* 13(1), 32-44, Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED580939.pdf>
- Osakwe, R. (2010). The Relationship Between Principal's Supervisory Strategies and Teachers' Instructional Performance in Delta North Senatorial District, Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(6), 437-440
<https://doi.org/10.3923/pjssci.2010.437.440>
- Pajak, E. (2010). The History and Future of Instructional Supervision in the United States. *Uluslararası Katılımlı Ulusal Eğitim Denetimi Kongresi* (pp. 1-19). Kutahya: Dumlupınar Üniversitesi
- Panigrahi, M.R. (2012). Implementation of Instructional Supervision in Secondary School: Approaches, Prospects and Problems. *Science, Technology and Arts Research Journal*, 1(3): 59-67

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Rhinehart, A.J. (2015). Lived Experiences of Beginning Counselors in Harmful Supervision. University of Tennessee, Tennessee. Knoxville Retrieved from <https://trace.tennessee.edu/utkgraddiss/3460>

Stark, D., McGhee, M.W., & Jimerson, J.B. (2017). Reclaiming Instructional Supervision Using Solution – Focused Strategies to Promote Teacher Development. *Journal of Research on Leadership Education*. 12(3), 215-238
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1942775116684895>

Sooksomchitra, A. (2020). Supervision State of Professional Experience Practice in Faculty of Education, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. In *International Academic Multidisciplinary Research Conference in Cape Town, South Africa* (pp. 35-39)

Soltani, M. (2014). What is Quality? Retrieved 20th July, 2020 from www.lifetime-reliability.com/cms/free-article/work

Son, E., & Ellis, M.V. (2013) A Cross- Cultural Comparison of Clinical Supervision in South Korea and the United States. *Psychotherapy*, 50, 189-205. Crossref, Medline,

Sullivan, S., & Glanz, J. (2013). *Supervision that Improves Teaching and Learning: Strategies and Techniques* (4th Ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE

Tyagi, R.S. (2010). School – Based Instructional Supervision and the Effective Professional Development of Teachers. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and*

International Education, 40(1), 111-125.
[Htpps://doi.org/10.1080/03057920902909485](https://doi.org/10.1080/03057920902909485)

Tubosun, B., Umar, H., (2016). School Administration and Instructional Supervision of Secondary School Chemistry for Students' Academic Performance. *Iss. Sci. Res.* 1(3), 27-36

Wanzare, Z. (2011). Instructional Supervision in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya. *Educational Management Administration and Leadership*, 40(2), 188-216
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143211427977>

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Watkins, C.E., Jr. (2012). Psychotherapy Supervision in the New Millennium: Competency

– Based, Evidence – Based, Particularized, and Energized. *Journal of Contemporary Psychotherapy*, 42, 193-203 Cross Ref

Williams, J., Baksh, T. A., & James, F. (2019). Transforming Teachers' Instructional Practices through Clinical Supervision. *Caribbean Curriculum*, Vol 26, 131-152
<https://>

uwspace.sta.uwi.edu/dspace/bitstream/handle/2139/49430/Transforming%20Teachers%20Instructional%20Practices%20Through%20Clinical%20Supervision.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum **International Editor:** Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT *Multidisciplinary e-Publication*

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024) / International Circulation
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

BIO NOTE

Hershey M. Lacambra is a dedicated and ever – hardworking teacher. She has been a volunteer teacher in a Pre - Kindergarten program then later on becomes an elementary school teacher for more than two years. Her work centers on ways in which educational practices can be made more equitable. Her research focuses on clinical instructional supervision in schools. At present, she works as the Program Head of the College of Education in World Citi Colleges in Guimba, Nueva Ecija.

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.10491778](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10491778)

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.